

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Somatic embryogenesis in wild rice *Oryza perennis* Moench

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Wild rice species *O. perennis* Moench is tolerant of stagnant flooding and acid sulfate soils and has desirable floral characteristics for outcrossing.

We sterilized and cultured young inflorescences and the scutellum of mature seeds of *O. perennis*. Embryogenic calli (E-callus) and nonembryogenic calli (NE-callus) were initiated from both explants (see figure). E-callus induction frequency was higher in young inflorescences (62%) than in mature seeds (44%). The embryogenic nature of the callus cultures from both explants was maintained over 14 subculture passages (about 16 mo).

Regeneration frequency and average green plant production of the callus derived from young inflorescences decreased with time in culture (see table).

In seed-derived callus, there was no clear trend in the percentage of calli responding. However, average green plant production showed a decreasing trend. Generally, a decline in regeneration capacity of the callus and in average green plant production was observed.

Although the regeneration capacity of both explants did not differ significantly,

from a practical point of view mature seed is a more convenient source of explant than a young inflorescence because it can be stored and is more readily available any time of the year.

Two types of callus formed from scutellum of mature seed after 4 wk in culture.

The effect of different concentrations of BAP (2, 4, 6, and 8 mg/liter) on plant regeneration at passage 8 was determined. The optimum level was 4 mg/liter, which gave the highest callus response and average green plant regeneration in both explants.

Plant regeneration through somatic embryogenesis was proven by longitudinal section and scanning electron microscopy. Structures of somatic embryos resembled those of IR40.

This is the first report on somatic embryogenesis from a wild rice species. Young inflorescences and scutellum of mature seeds appear to be appropriate explants for establishing wild rice species plants via somatic embryogenesis. □

Plant regeneration at different durations in culture of calli derived from young inflorescences and seeds of *O. perennis*.^a IRRI, 1987.

Passage (mo in culture)	Young inflorescence-derived callus				Seed-derived callus			
	Calli plated (no.)	Calli responding ^b (%)	Total plants produced (no.)	Av green plant production ^c (no.)	Calli plated (no.)	Calli responding ^b (%)	Total plants produced (no.)	Av green plant production ^c (no.)
6-8	25	80	117	5.8	20	75.0	97	6.5
7-9	20	65	78	6.0	20	50.0	58	5.8
8-10	20	60	62	5.2	15	66.7	60	6.0
9-11	25	60	64	4.3	12	58.3	35	5.0
10-12	20	60	42	3.5	43	69.8	132	4.4
11-13	34	58.8	70	3.5	20	65.0	52	4.0
12-14	34	35.3	43	3.6	20	70.0	57	4.1
13-15	20	40	24	3.0	30	66.7	65	3.3
14-16	20	45	20	2.2	30	53.3	17	1.1

^aComputed after 4 wk in culture on MS₁₈₋₁ medium.

^b $\frac{\text{Total no. calli responding}}{\text{Total no. calli plated for regeneration}} \times 100$

^cPlants produced/calli-producing plant.